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A novel strategy for the synthesis of 6H-chromeno [4, 3-*b*] quinoline by intramolecular Heck cyclization

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Abstract

A novel procedure for the synthesis of various derivatives of 6H-chromeno [4, 3-*b*] quinolines from intramolecular Heck reaction of 2-chloro-3-(phoxymethyl) quinolines is described in this study. Intramolecular cyclization of *N*-alkylated indoles was efficiently investigated as well. The reaction is catalyzed by bis (triphenylphosphine) palladium (II) dichloride in acetonitrile at 80 °C.

Graphical Abstract

Keywords: Intramolecular Heck Reaction; 6H-chromeno [4,3-*b*] quinolines; Palladium; Indole.